

IMPROVING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF A RE WATER DESALINATION PROTOTYPE

Ayad Alwaer and Jasson Gryzagoridis.

Abstract:

The paper presents results obtained when utilizing an evacuated tube heat pipe solar collector and associated equipment as a prototype water desalination system. Data were obtained indoors using a solar simulator as a renewable energy (RE) source, during experiments conducted on the prototype. During the initial stages of developing the prototype, a reasonable amount of water was harvested with the system under vacuum conditions (70 kPa below atmospheric pressure), and later with extra insulation material wrapped around the geyser. After doubling the copper pipe vapour outlet of the geyser for the vapour to flow to the condenser, the system's performance proved superior to all previous attempts in raising the level of the yield of distillate. A notable improvement in the yield of pure water production was obtained, as demonstrated by a striking rise in efficiency from 11% to 38.2%.

Keywords:

desalination system; evacuated tube solar collector; heat pipe technology; solar energy; insulation material.

**Corresponding Author Email: ayss732001@gmail.com*

I. INTRODUCTION

It is very disturbing to contemplate the future of our world when less than half a percent of the Earth's total water resources is available as pure water for direct human use, or for agricultural and industrial consumption, [1]. Most of the earth's available water contains a lot of salt, making it unsuitable for use as drinkable water, however desalination processes are a solution to making more potable water available.

One of the main types of water desalination is the process of water distillation, which involves heating it to the point of boiling, thus producing vapour. Most desalination plants use fossil fuels for freshwater production adding more problems for humanity in terms of environmental pollution and because of depletion of the deposits of fossil fuels, higher energy costs. The use of renewable energy such as solar irradiance can produce the range of temperatures of 70 to 120 °C with currently available solar water heating equipment [2].

The history of solar desalination technology possibly began in the fourth-century BC, when Aristotle outlined methods of evaporating seawater

and then condensing it to produce drinkable water, [3]. In the fifteenth century Arab alchemists supplied mineworkers with drinkable water while they worked. Prototypes similar to these old distillers still exist today [4]. The nineteenth century witnessed major applications of the method of solar distillation for desalination. The first patent for distillation of water by solar energy was issued in 1870 in Las Salinas, Chile [5].

Solar desalination (indirect or solar-driven) developed after the 1980s when concentrating collectors as well as flat plate collectors became commercialized. The creation of vacuum between the absorber and the cover of a solar collector resulted in an improvement in efficiency due to minimizing the heat losses by conduction and convection [2]. Modern solar water heating equipment utilizing heat pipes in evacuated tubes are on the increase worldwide [6].

The objectives of this paper is to report on the work focused on potable water yielded by a commercially available solar water heating system encompassing evacuated heat pipe technology. By systematically altering certain parameters of the prototype the potable water yield increased.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE SOLAR WATER DESALINATION PROTOTYPE

A new system of seawater desalination has been developed during this research work as shown in its final form in Fig 1.

Fig. 1 schematic of the prototype tested at 70 kPa below atmospheric pressure with double 76 mm dia. copper pipe vapour outlet

In the prototype's 'geyser' containing saline water, vapour is created by the heat harvested from the available solar energy, using an evacuated tube heat pipe solar collector. The vapour is passed through the condenser to produce fresh water (distillate). As a result of continuous evaporation, the concentration of minerals dissolved in the water (including salt), will increase and eventually saturate the contents of the geyser. In order to refresh the water, the mineral-saturated water will be discharged via a drain created at the bottom of the geyser. The basic system of the water desalination prototype, as shown in Figure 2, is comprised of the following components:

- 1-The feed tank
- 2-The condenser
- 3-The geyser
- 4-Variable voltage transformer - Variac
- 5-The 12 vacuum tube heat pipe solar collector
- 6-The sun simulator comprised of 12 halogen lamps
- 7-Fresh water tank
- 8-Circulating pump
- 9-Rotary vane vacuum pump
- 10-Pressure gauge
- 11-Steam pipes
- 12-The thermocouples
- 13-Thermocouples to data logger
- 14-Tube to determine and control the water level inside the geyser
- 15-Flow meter
- 16-Circulating pump

17-Drain valve

Fig. 2 Photograph of the solar water desalination prototype

III. MODIFICATIONS TO THE GEYSER

Many of the modifications to the geyser were as a result of testing the system's performance in terms of distillate harvest and are summarized as follows:

- The original copper coil heat exchanger was replaced with a new heat exchanger consisting of six 22 mm dia. copper pipe sections, approximately 900 mm long. The new heat exchanger increased the heat transfer surface area from the original value of 0.15 m² to 0.373 m² (2.5 times larger).
- Initial tests yielded very little distillate and to increase the heat input into the water the heater was removed and the geyser's water became the carrier of heat from the collector's manifold.
- It was realized that the relatively small vapour outlet of 16 mm dia. and its original position were causing restriction of the flow of steam being generated. The outlet of the steam was changed from the side exit to a top exit and increased to a 76 mm dia. by cutting a hole into the top of the geyser and welding a steam socket. This represents an increase in flow area of 21.4 times compared to the original outlet.
- It was observed that considerable heat was lost from the system during periods of inactivity (i.e. during the night when the sun simulator was turned off). For the purpose of reducing these overnight heat losses from the system, a standard blanket was wrapped around the geyser and the test results indicated a fair improvement over the previous yield.
- Based on the previous increase of distillate harvest after the modifications to the geyser's vapour outlet,

the process was repeated by adding another 76 mm dia. copper pipe outlet. The two outlets were insulated and joined together at a point below the water level in Tank no 2. The vapour outlet was then 42.8 times larger than the original.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL

The working prototype of the solar-powered desalination plant, illustrated in Figures 1 and 2, was assembled in a laboratory in Mechanical Engineering Department at the Bellville Campus of the Cape Peninsula University of Technology. Indoor experiments facilitated the collection of data because environmental disturbances were minimized and the solar simulator maintained a constant energy input. A period of 7 hours of operation per day was chosen with an average irradiance from the sun simulator at 682 watts/m², typical of Cape Town condition.

- At start, the system was charged by inserting 110 liters of water into the geyser.
- All valves were appropriately set so as to facilitate the flow of condensate, vapour and working fluid.
- Water temperatures (circulating working fluid) at the collector's manifold inlet and outlet positions were recorded.
- The temperatures of the water in different positions in the geyser were similarly recorded.
- The solar simulator was turned on.
- The system's circulating pump (collector's manifold to geyser) was set to maximum capacity.
- The flow rate of the working fluid (water) was recorded using the flow meter.
- After a period of one hour, all temperatures were recorded.
- For seven hours, the various temperatures were recorded in 60-minute intervals.
- The system was shut down (both pump and lamps were switched off).
- The system was checked for levels of condensate collected during the test period.
- The following day, at start all temperatures were recorded, the solar simulator and the circulating pump were turned on for the next seven hours of testing.

Tests were performed with the prototype system for each modification on the geyser and also under lower than atmospheric pressures.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Twelve experiments were conducted to test the prototype, with the results summarized in Table 1. Table 1 presents a description of the tests that were performed subsequent to various modifications made to the solar desalination plant prototype, coupled to the quantity of water harvested and efficiency of its production.

For reasons of this paper's brevity, Table 2 displays only sample data (pertinent to the typical results presented further down the text) that were collected daily during the five days' period for each test. For the same reason, the individual readings of the four thermocouples located in the geyser are represented with their average value $T_{avg0/1}$ and instead of all the daily hourly data obtained only the start middle and end data are displayed. The flow rate of the working fluid circulating through the collector's manifold to the geyser was recorded as 13.5 liters per minute. The authors chose to include the calculated values of Q_1 and Q_2 in Table 2, in order to facilitate the reader when perusing some of the charts that are displayed further in the text. Using the data from Table 2 the amount of heat that was transported by the working fluid from the collector's manifold to the geyser is evaluated by the average instantaneous readings of the two sets of temperatures that were recorded every hour. This temperature difference multiplied by the flow rate and specific heat gives the average watts, which are delivered to the geyser.

$$Q_1 = \dot{m} C_p (T_2 - T_1) \dots (1)$$

Where Q_1 is the heat transferred in watts, \dot{m} is the flow rate in liters per minute, C_p is the specific heat of water (4186) Joules/kg °C and T_1 and T_2 are the inlet and outlet temperatures (in degrees centigrade), at the collector's manifold. Through the heat exchange between the manifold and the geyser, heat was transferred to the 110 liters of water and raised its temperature accordingly.

The average temperature in four locations in the geyser was recorded hourly and used to calculate the amount of heat transferred.

$$Q_2 = m C_p (T_{avg1} - T_{avg0})/\Delta t \dots (2)$$

Where Q_2 is the heat increase into the geyser's bulk water having a mass (m) in kg equivalent to the 110 liters, T_{avg0} and T_{avg1} are the average bulk water temperature in the geyser recorded.

Table 1 Total water harvested (ml) and best daily efficiency of water production with each modification of the system

Test No.	Description of the test	Total water harvested ml	Water production efficiency% (test's last day)
1	Commercial/original design of geyser with its original heat exchanger.	0.00	0.00
2	The geyser after replacing the original heat exchanger with a larger one.	2230	11
3	Removal of the heat exchanger (System's performance test at normal (Atm.) pressure).	2415	14
4	System's performance test at pressure of (Atm. 50kPa below Atm.)	3080	16.34
5	Change the size of the vapour pipe outlet to (760mm) System's performance test at normal (Atm.) pressure	6110	27.13
6	System's performance test at pressure of (50 kPa below Atm.), with the new vapour outlet pipe (760mm).	6300	26.96
7	System's performance test at pressure of (70kPa below Atm.).	7500	31.44
8	Enhancement of the geyser's insulation (extra layer of insulation material), at normal pressure.	9130	32.99
9	At pressure of (50kPa below Atm.), after step 8.	9550	30.55
10	At pressure of (70kPa below Atm.) after step 8.	10560	34.12
11	Doubling the vapour pipe outlet (760 mm x2), at normal pressure, commercial insulation material.	8300	29.58
12	Under pressure of (70kPa below Atm.), with extra layer of insulation material.	12750	38.21

Table 2 Selected data from the test

Time	T ₁	T ₂	T _{avg0/1}	Q ₁	Q ₂
	°C	°C	°C	watts	watts
Day 1					
09:23:36	23.1	23.1	23.1	0.0	0.0
13:23:36	45.2	46.4	45.1	1095.5	719.5
16:23:36	60.9	62.0	60.8	1017.3	640.3
Day 2				7114.8	4817.2
09:23:36	52.5	52.5	52.5	0.0	0.0
13:23:36	72.1	73.1	72.0	945.3	572.8
16:23:36	84.0	85.0	83.9	918.0	479.3
Day 3				6222.3	4020.5
09:23:36	66.2	66.2	66.2	0.0	0.0
13:23:36	83.1	84.1	83.0	938.7	490.7
16:23:36	93.4	94.4	93.4	885.9	422.5
Day 4				6032.5	3480.9
09:23:36	72.6	72.6	72.6	0.0	0.0
13:23:36	87.6	88.7	87.6	966.5	416.3
16:23:36	95.3	96.3	95.3	940.1	294.9
Day 5				6273.1	2895.3
09:23:36	70.7	70.7	70.7	0.0	0.0
13:23:36	85.8	86.8	85.7	965.1	419.7
16:23:36	93.8	94.7	93.7	910.9	306.3
				6250.5	2949.1

Fig. 3 Comparison of heat available in the collector's manifold and heat obtained by the water in the geyser

Figure 3 serves to illustrate the system's behaviour on the first day of the test. Figure 4 illustrates the behaviour of the system five days toward the end of the test. Attention is drawn toward the end of day five (last hour). The heat available in the manifold no longer was entirely utilized to increase the geyser's bulk water temperature (indicated at this stage as avg. 93.7°C) but went into producing vapour.

Fig. 4 The system's behaviour regarding available heat to it and the inability to increase its energy level because active vaporization has been established

During the five-day period for the test the system acquired the total sum of approximately 18160 watts to reach the level of producing vapour only. Fig. 5 is presented because it demonstrates the performance of the system's geyser during the entire period of the five days' test. During the first day's seven-hour heating period the largest bulk temperature increase was observed for the water in the geyser. During the inactivity for the remaining first day's 17 hours, heat was lost from the geyser to the surrounding ambient which is demonstrated by the drop in the geyser bulk water temperature. Subsequent heating and cooling of the geyser's average water temperature behaviour was as expected i.e. lesser increase in average water temperature and larger heat loss during the cooling period. Figure 6 serves to illustrate the manner by which the system acquired its daily energy during the test.

Fig. 5 Heating and cooling of geyser's water temperature during the test

Fig. 6 Level of daily system's energy acquisition

Similarly, during the inactivity periods of 17 hours daily, the geyser lost energy to the ambient amounting to a total of more than 9000 watts. Figure 7 illustrates the level of heat loss from the geyser during each period of inactivity and as expected it did increase during each inactivity period as the geyser's bulk temperature had increased during the previous irradiance period of seven hours.

Typical graphical display of the production of distillate daily harvest during the test, culminating at the total during the 5 days is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8 shows the amount of water that has been desalinated (daily and in total) with reduced geyser pressure and double 76mm dia. vapour outlet pipe after the addition of the extra insulation on the geyser. In terms of water productivity in this test, the yield of the pure water increased, reaching 12750 ml per test, as shown in the last test No. 12 in Table 1.

Fig. 7 Serves to illustrate the manner by which the system acquired its daily energy during the test

Fig. 8 Daily and totally of water amounts produced

Figure 9 is presented as a graphical representation of part of Table 1, serving the purpose of easing the comparison of the prototype's performance in terms of its distillate yield after the various modifications and testing procedures that were adopted during this work. The performance of the system in terms of producing a certain quantity of distilled water and its efficiency in doing so in the last day of the various tests is shown in Figures 10 and 11 respectively.

Fig. 9 Comparison of total (five days) distillate yield from the twelve tests

Fig. 10 Comparison of the distillate yields from the last day per each test

Fig. 11 The efficiencies in terms of pure water production on the last day of each test

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the work associated with the development of a prototype water desalination assembly which was tested in a laboratory. In a series of several distinct experiments, a commercially available domestic, evacuated tube (incorporating heat pipes) solar water heating system, with auxiliary equipment such as vacuum and circulating pumps, condenser etc. was systematically tested after modifications to the geyser and changes of its pressure. Based on the principle that water boils at a lower temperature with

decreased pressure, by slightly evacuating the geyser, increased amounts of pure water were obtained, thus it can be claimed as a form of enhancement of the performance of the system. Using the science of classical thermodynamics and of heat transfer the performance of the prototype plant was evaluated on the basis of heat balance and energy transfer on the relevant components of the plant. The test performed on the system at a pressure of 70 kPa below atmospheric pressure with the double 76mm dia. vapour outlet pipe and after the addition of the extra insulation on the geyser as anticipated proved encouraging. Toward the end of the fifth day of irradiance the system reached the energy level required to start producing a reasonable yield of potable water at a rate of 12.750 liters for the test period, which compares favorably with previous results of 10.5 liters /test. By reducing heat losses with the addition of extra insulation material on the geyser significantly improved the yield of distilled water. The accumulation of salt after a number of desalination cycles was not dealt with. However, there is a provision of draining the geyser's contents through a hole that was provided at the bottom and thus it is possible to clean it and replenish with fresh sea water. The overall outcome of these experiments showed an improvement on the yield of desalinated water from 2230 to 12750 ml, thus raising the efficiency of pure water production from 11% to 38.2%.

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Author Biographical Statements

Ayad A. Alwaer, holds a B.Sc. degree in physics from Faculty of Science, Bani Waleed, Libya in 2000, M.Sc. in Energy Conservation and Management from Tabbin Institute for Metallurgical Studies (TIMS) Egypt in 2007 and D.Tech. In Mechanical engineering from Cape Peninsula University of Technology (CPUT). He is an Assistant Professor and currently a director of the scientific affairs and senior lecturer at the Renewable Energies Technologies at Higher institute of Science and technology Tarhuna-Libya

Jasson Gryzagoridis. Pr. Eng. BSc, MSc, PhD is a registered professional engineer, and holds degrees from Lamar University, Texas A&M University and the University of Cape Town respectively. He is an Adjunct Professor acting as post graduate student's mentor at the Mech. Eng. Department at Cape Peninsula University of Technology (CPUT)